

Effect of Altered Thyroid Hormone (FT3 & FT4) and TSH Levels on Sepsis Related Neonatal MortalityGurjar Umesh Kumar¹, Kumari Sushila², Meena Kailash Kumar³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatric, SMS Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan (India)²Post graduate Student, Department of Paediatric, SMS Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan (India)³Senior Professor & Superintendent, Sir Padampat Institute of Neonatal and Paediatric Health, Department of Paediatric, SMS Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan (India)

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aims and Objectives:** To study the effect of altered thyroid hormone (FT3&FT4) and TSH levels on Sepsis related neonatal mortality.**Study Design:** It was a hospital based observational, Analytical study, 32 Term babies with sepsis were taken, Thyroid hormones (FT3&FT4) and TSH levels from the blood collected between 18 and 24 hr after birth were measured by Chemiluminescence immunoassay. Outcome results were analysed using chi square, and ROC curve. P value <0.05 was considered significant.**Results:** Cases of Neonatal sepsis expired had significant low level of S.FT4 (1.22 ± 0.27 ng/dl) as compare to discharged (1.58 ± 0.38 ng/dl), but there was no significant difference observed in S.FT3 and TSH level. Cut off value of S. FT4 ≤ 1.39 ng/dl & S. TSH ≤ 3.8 8uIU/ml combined was having a good predictive value (SN- 77.2, SP- 90, PPV- 94.44 & NPV- 64.29) for Sepsis related neonatal mortality.**Conclusions:** Cut off value of combined S. FT4 ≤ 1.39 ng/dl & S.TSH ≤ 3.8 8uIU/ml have best predictive value for Sepsis related neonatal mortality.**Keyword:** Sepsis, Neonatal Mortality, Thyroid Hormones, Hypothyroidism.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Thyroid hormones play an important part in the synthesis of mitochondrial enzymes and structural elements; in addition they have role in the thermogenesis, water and electrolyte transportation and in the growth and development of central nervous system [1]. Previous studies shows that low levels of thyroid hormone in non-thyroid illnesses have been associated with a poor prognosis and high mortality [2].

The objective of our study was to study the effect of altered thyroid hormones (FT3&FT4) & TSH levels on Sepsis related neonatal mortality. And to determine whether we can use the serum levels of these hormones to predict sepsis related mortality.

Material & Methods

A hospital based prospective, observational, analytical study was conducted in the Neonatal units of Department of Pediatrics S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur during the period of May 2020 to August 2021. Detailed history was taken, that included antenatal, natal and postnatal history, detailed physical examination was done and clinical course of these newborns were followed during their

hospital stay (Discharged/Expired). Neonates having Sepsis, as per NNF definition [3] were considered and were included in the study.

The neonate of mothers who had used antihypertensive, corticosteroids, thyroid or antithyroid drugs during pregnancy, Preterm babies of <37 wk of age, neonates with perinatal asphyxia, metabolic disorders or any congenital malformations and parent of newborn that refuse to give consent were excluded from the study.

Considering a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$ (type1 error) and a statistical power of 90% ($B=0.10$) to detect a difference of 0.95, in the level of FT4, the sample size required was 30, we included 32 newborns.

Cases underwent physical examination including their neurological assessment and sepsis score as per NNF definition [4]. In all study subjects, serum FT3, FT4 and TSH were measured between 18 and 24 hours of life. Blood sampling included 5 ml of blood in a plain vial collected and processed within 2-3 hours of sampling. Meanwhile, the samples were stored at room temperature only.

Chemiluminiscence immunoassay was used for the determination of hormone levels. All samples were tested at central laboratory SMS hospital Jaipur, blinded to the patient’s data. FT3 values were expressed in pg/ml; FT4 values were expressed in ng/dl and TSH values were expressed in uIu/ml.

Statistical analysis was performed with the SPSS, version 20 for Windows statistical software package (SPSS inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

Mean and SD compared using student ‘t’ test. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was performed to determine the optimal cut off values of significant variables. Probability P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 32 septic newborns were included in the study and the clinical course was followed until final outcome either they Expired or Discharged from the hospital. In our study a total of 10 out of the 32 (31.25%) cases expired. This percentage was much higher 8 out of 10 (80%) among babies with severe sepsis. In our study significantly lower mean S.FT4 (ng/dl) was observed among the 10 expired cases (1.22±0.27) as compared to 22 Discharged (1.58±0.38) cases. No significant difference was observed in S.FT3 (pg/ml) [Expired 2.63±0.91, V/S Discharged 3.15±0.88] and TSH (uIu/ml) [Expired 5.01±2.58, V/S Discharged 7.34±3.52] levels. (Table 1)

Table 1: Comparison of Neonatal Outcome in relation to Thyroid Hormone Profile

Outcome		S.FT3(pg/ml)	S.FT4(ng/dl)	TSH(uIu/ml)
Discharged (N=22)	Mean	3.15	1.58	7.34
	SD	0.88	0.38	3.52
Expired (N=10)	Mean	2.63	1.22	5.01
	SD	0.91	0.27	2.58
P Value LS		0.139NS	<0.05S	0.07NS

In our study we also tried to find the sensitivity and specificity of Thyroid hormones and TSH levels for predicting mortality in septic babies.

To get the data in form of true positives and negatives and false positives and negatives, we need to decide a cut off value for these tests.

For this purpose ROC Curves were used.

S.FT3 Level for prediction of sepsis related mortality at the optimal cut-off points of the ROC analysis curves.

The ROC curve of FT3 for predicting death in septic neonates was constructed. The area under curve (AUC) was found to be 0.156 (95% confidence interval =0.044 to 0.267). The optimum cut off value was obtained by points of test values that grants the highest Youden Index that is (SN+SP)-1. The best cut off value for S FT3 for predicting mortality was ≥1.43uIu/ml (at youdon index 0.019 where max SN And SP exist) Sensitivity 32% and specificity 0.02% was determined with SE 0.101. This was not found to be a good predictive test.

Figure 1: ROC plot of S.FT3 in reference to death in Septic neonates

S.FT4 Level for prediction of sepsis related mortality at the optimal cut-off points of the ROC analysis curves.

The ROC curve of S.FT4 (ng/dl) for predicting death in septic neonates was constructed. The area under curve (AUC) was found to be 0.8 (95% confidence interval =0.623 to 0.977).

The optimum cut off value was obtained by points of test values that grants the highest Youden Index that is (SN+SP)-1.

The best cut off value for S FT4 for predicting mortality was ≤ 1.39 (at youdon index 0.527 where max SN And SP exist) Sensitivity 72.7% and specificity 80%, was determined with SE 0.09.

Figure 2: ROC plot of S.FT4 in reference to death in septic neonates

S.TSH Level for Sepsis related mortality at the optimal cut-off points of the ROC analysis curves.

The ROC curve of TSH for predicting death in asphyxiated neonates was constructed. The area under curve (AUC) was found to be 0.7 (95% confidence interval =0.502 to 0.898). The optimum

cut off value was obtained by points of test values that grants the highest Youden Index that is (SN+SP)-1.

The best cut off value for S TSH for predicting mortality was ≤ 3.88 u/ml (at youdon index 0.364 where max SN And SP exist) Sensitivity 86.4% and specificity 50%, was determined with SE 0.101.

Figure 3: ROC plot of TSH in reference to death in septic neonates

Table 2: Predictive value of cut off level of S.FT4 < 1.39 ng/dl, S.TSH < 3.88 uIu/ml and combined S.FT4 (< 1.39 ng/dl) & S.TSH for (< 3.88 uIu/ml) for neonatal mortality in newborns with Sepsis

Cutoff value	Predicted Outcome	Observed Outcome			Sensitivity	Specificity	Positive Predictive Value	Negative Predictive Value
		Expired	Discharged	Total				
S.FT4 < 1.39 ng/dl	Expired	8	6	14				
	Discharged	2	16	18	72.73	80	88.89	57.14
	Total	10	22	32				
S.TSH < 3.88 uIu/ml	Expired	5	3	8				
	Discharged	5	19	24	86.36	50	79.17	62.5
	Total	10	22	32				
Combined S.FT4 (<1.39ng/dl)&S.TSH (< 3.88 uIu/ml)	Expired	9	5	14				
	Discharged	1	17	18	77.27	90	94.44	64.29
	Total	10	22	32				

Our results shows that a cut off value of S.FT4 \leq 1.39 ng/dl is having SN- 72.73, SP- 80, PPV- 88.89 & NPV- 57.14, cut off value of S.TSH \leq 3.88 uIu/ml is having SN- 86.36, SP- 50, PPV- 79.17 & NPV- 62.5 and cut off value of S.FT4 \leq 1.39 ng/dl & S.TSH \leq 3.88 uIu/ml combined was having SN- 77.2, SP- 90, PPV- 94.44 & NPV- 64.29. Sensitivity 32% and specificity 0.02 % was determined with SE 0.101 from ROC curve for S.FT3. This was not found to be a good predictive test.

Sensitivity of cut off level of S.FT4 (< 1.39 ng/dl) for predicting mortality in Septic newborns is good (73%) with high specificity (80%) and positive predictive value(89%). Sensitivity of cut off level of S.TSH (< 3.88 uIu/ml) for predicting mortality in Septic newborns is higher (86%) than S.FT4 but specificity (50%) is not so good. Our observations shows that a cut off value of S.FT4 \leq 1.39 ng/dl & S.TSH \leq 3.88 uIu/ml combined is having a good (SN- 77.2, SP- 90, PPV- 94.44 & NPV- 64.29) predictive value for Sepsis related neonatal mortality compared to S.FT4 or S.TSH alone.

Discussion

In our study, we assessed thyroid hormone and TSH levels in the blood (between 18 and 24 h after birth) of newborns with Sepsis in order to investigate the effect of these hormone concentrations on outcome. We also tried to find the sensitivity and specificity of Thyroid hormones and TSH levels for predicting mortality in Septic babies. To get the data in form of true positives and negatives and false positives and negatives, we need to decide a cut off value for these tests. For this purpose ROC Curves were used.

The best cut off value for S FT3 for predicting mortality was \geq 1.43uIu/ml (at youdon index 0.019 where max SN And Sp exist) Sensitivity 32% and specificity 0.02% was determined with SE 0.101.

This was not found to be a good predictive test. The best cut off value for S. FT4 for predicting mortality was \leq 1.39 ng/dl (at youdon index 0.527

where max SN And Sp exist) with Sensitivity 72.7% and specificity 80% (determined with SE 0.09).

The best cut off value for S. TSH for predicting mortality was \leq 3.88 uIu/ml (at youdon index 0.364 where max SN And Sp exist) (Sensitivity 86.4% and specificity and 50%), was determined with SE 0.101.

To determine the Predictive value of S.FT4, TSH and combined FT4 & TSH for mortality among sepsis cases tables were constructed separately for S.FT4, S.TSH and for combined S.FT4 & TSH. From these tables sensitivity, specificity and positive & negative predictive values were obtained for each parameter.

Our results shows that a cut off value of S.FT4 \leq 1.39 ng/dl is having SN- 72.73, SP- 80, PPV- 88.89 & NPV- 57.14, cut off value of S.TSH \leq 3.88 uIu/ml is having SN- 86.36, SP- 50, PPV- 79.17 & NPV- 62.5 and cut off value of S.FT4 \leq 1.39 ng/dl & S. TSH \leq 3.88 uIu/ml is having SN- 77.2, SP- 90, PPV- 94.44 & NPV- 64.29 when these two used combindly.

Study done by DN Pereira et al [5] of the 11 baby from the sepsis with FT4 < 2.0 ng/dl between 18 and 24 hr of life, 6(54.5%) died. There were no deaths among the 6 neonates with FT4 > 2.0 ng/dl ($p=0.0427$). Low FT4 presented 100% sensitivity (CI 95%, 52-100) and 55% specificity (CI 95%, 25-82) in predicting death of septic neonates. The positive predictive value was 55% (CI 95%, 25-82) and the negative predictive value was 100% (CI 95%, 52-100). They have not studied effect of TSH.

Our observations showed that a cut off value of S.FT4 \leq 1.39 ng/dl & S.TSH \leq 3.88 uIu/ml combined was having a good predictive value for Sepsis related neonatal mortality. However a larger study is needed to verify our observations and to make further recommendations.

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